

CLASSICAL YOGAS IN KARNA ROGAS AS PER CHAKRADATTA**Ankush Kumar^{1*}, Vijayant Bhardwaj², Satish Kumar Sharma³, Akanksha⁴**¹M.D. Scholar, ²Professor & Head of Department, ⁴M.D. Scholar^{1,2,4}Department of Shalaky Tantra, Rajiv Gandhi Government Post Graduate
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Attribution 4.0 International license.**ABSTRACT**

Karnaroga (ear disorders) are extensively described in *Ayurveda* and are primarily attributed to the vitiation of *Doshas*, especially *Vata* and *Kapha*, affecting the structures of the ear. *Chakradatta*, a renowned classical compendium, provides a systematic and clinically oriented description of various *Karna Rogas* along with effective therapeutic formulations (*Yogas*). The text emphasizes both *Shamana* (palliative) and *Shodhana* (purificatory) approaches, with special importance given to localized therapies such as *Karna Purana*, *Nasya*, *Dhoopana*, and internal administration of herbo-mineral formulations. Classical *Yogas* described in *Chakradatta* - including medicated oils, powders, decoctions and *Ghrilas* are selected based on *Dosha* predominance and disease presentation, aiming to alleviate pain, discharge, hearing impairment and inflammation. These formulations act by pacifying vitiated *Doshas*, strengthening auditory structures

and restoring normal ear function. The present review attempts to compile and critically analyze the classical *Yogas* indicated for *Karnaroga* as described in *Chakradatta*, highlighting their composition, indications, and therapeutic relevance. This study underscores the significance of these time-tested formulations in the effective management of ear disorders and their potential applicability in contemporary clinical practice.

KEYWORDS: *Karna Roga, Chakradatta, Karnashoola, Classical Yogas in Karna Rogas, Karna Purana.*

INTRODUCTION

Karnaroga (ear disorders) are comprehensively described in Ayurvedic literature, with detailed classification based on etiopathogenesis, clinical presentation and *Dosha* predominance. Disorders of the ear significantly affect hearing, communication, and balance, thereby impairing the quality of life. Classical texts attribute the manifestation of *Karnarogas* mainly to the vitiation of *Vata* and *Kapha*, though *Pitta* involvement is observed in conditions associated with suppuration, discharge and inflammation. Improper dietary habits, exposure to cold and moisture, trauma, infestation by organisms and neglect of ear hygiene are recognized as important causative factors.

Chakradatta stands out as a therapeutically oriented classical text that offers a concise yet systematic exposition of disease-specific formulations. It provides an extensive description of *Karnarogas* such as *Karnashoola, Karnanada, Karna Badhirya, Karnastrava, Pootikarna, Karnanadi, Krimikarna* and *Durviddha Karna*, along with clearly indicated classical *Yogas* for each condition. These formulations are primarily intended for local administration through *Karnapurana, Karna Prakshalana, Karna Dhoopana, Nasya, Lepa* and *Abhyanga*, emphasizing the importance of localized therapeutic interventions in the management of ear disorders.

The *Yogas* described in *Chakradatta* include a wide range of medicated oils (*Taila*), fresh juices (*Swarasa*), powders (*Churna*), decoctions, alkaline preparations (*Kshara*), animal products and mineral drugs. These formulations are selected based on the specific pathology and *Dosha* involvement, aiming to alleviate pain, discharge, tinnitus, hearing loss, foul odour and parasitic infestation, while simultaneously promoting healing and restoration of normal ear function. The frequent use of warming, penetrating and cleansing substances highlights the text's emphasis on pacifying *Vata* and *Kapha* and eliminating local *Dosha* accumulation. The present article aims to compile, categorize, and present the classical *Yogas* indicated for various *Karna Rogas* as described in *Chakradatta*. By systematically organizing these formulations under disease-specific headings, the study seeks to provide a comprehensive therapeutic reference for clinicians & researchers and to highlight the clinical relevance and applicability of these classical formulations in contemporary Ayurvedic practice.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The present study is a classical literary review undertaken to systematically compile and analyse the *Yogas* indicated for various *Karna Rogas* as described in *Chakradatta*.

The *Yogas* are described for conditions like *Karnashoola*, *Karnanada*, *Karna Badhirya*, *Karnastrava*, *Pootikarna*, *Karnanadi*, *Krimikarna*, *Karnapali Vardhana* and *Durviddha Karna*.

The selected *Yogas* are systematically compiled and categorized under individual disease headings.

Classical *Yogas* in *Karna Rogas*

Table 1: Showing number of *Yogas* described in various *Karna Rogas*.

Sr.No.	Disease(<i>Karna Roga</i>)	Numbering
A	<i>Karnashoola Yogas</i>	16
B	<i>Karnanada</i>	5
C	<i>Karna Badhirya</i>	5
D	<i>Karnastrava</i>	6
E	<i>Pootikarna</i>	11
F	<i>Karnanadi</i>	2
G	<i>Krimikarna</i>	4
H	<i>Karnapali Vardhana</i>	5
I	<i>Durviddha Karna</i>	1
	Total	55

A) *Karnashoola Yogas*

1. *Karnapurana* with the *Swarasa* of *Kapitha*, *Matulunga* and *Shringavera* is recommended in the management of *Karnashoola*.^[1]
2. *Karnapurana* with *Shringavera* mixed with *Madhu* and *Saindhava Lavana*, processed with *Taila* and administered in a mildly warm state.^[2]
3. A *Swarasa-Mishrana* prepared from *Lashuna*, *Arka*, *Shigru*, *Mulaka*, and *Kadali* is gently warmed and used for *Karnapurana*.^[3]
4. *Samudraphena Churna*^[4] is filled into the ear as a local therapeutic application.
5. *Karnapurana* is performed using the *Swarasa* of *Ardraka*, *Suryavarta*, *Shobhanjana*, and *Mulaka* either individually or in combination with *Madhu*, *Saindhava* and *Taila*.^[5]
6. *Shobhanjana Swarasa*^[6] mixed with *Tila Taila* is administered in a warm state for *Karnapurana*.
7. *Deepika Taila*^[7] *Karnapurana*.

8. *Arkapatra Swarasa*^[8] *Karnapurana*
9. *Vastamutra*^[9] *Karnapurana*.
10. *Vanshaneli Taila*^[10] *Karnapurana*.
11. *Hingwadi Taila*^[11] *Karnapurana*.
12. *Kshara Taila*^[12] *Karnapurana*.
13. *Madhushukta Dwayam Yoga*^[13] - A combination of *Madhu* and *Shukta* is used for *Karnapurana*.
14. *Ashtamutra* *Karnapurana*.^[14]
15. *Ashwathapatra Khalwa Taila* *Karnapurana*.^[15]
16. *Swarasa* extracted from *Snuhiksheera* by the *Arkapatraputa* method is slightly warmed and used for *Karnapurana*, which is stated to alleviate *Karnashoola*.^[16]

B) Karnanada Yogas

1. *Katu Taila* *Karnapurana*^[17]
2. *Apamarga Kshara Taila*^[18]
3. *Hingwadi Taila*^[19]
4. *Swarjikakshara Taila*^[20]
5. *Guda-Nagara Nasya*^[21]

C) Karna Badhirya Yogas

1. *Katu Taila* *Karnapurana*^[22]
2. *Swarjikakshara Taila*^[23]
3. *Bilva Taila*^[24]
4. *Apamarga Kshara Taila*^[25]
5. *Dashamoola Taila*^[26]

D) Karnastrava Yogas

1. *Swarjikakshara Taila*^[27]
2. *Panchavalkala Churna*,^[28] *Kapitha Rasa*, *Madhu* - *Karnapurana*
3. *Karpasphala Rasa*^[29] - *Karnapurana*
4. *Jambvadi Rasa Purana*^[30]
5. *Jambvadya Taila*^[31]
6. *Gondak Rasa Pryoga*^[32]

E) Pootikarna Yogas

1. *Gomutra Purana*^[33]
2. *Malatidala Rasa & Madhu Karnapurana*^[34]
3. *Harital & Gomutra Karnapurana*^[35]
4. *Nirgundyaadi Purana*^[36]
5. *Jati Tailam*^[37]
6. *Varunadi Taila*^[38]
7. *Guggulu Dhoopan*^[39]
8. *Rajvriksha Jala*^[40] – *Karna Prakshalana* and *Karnapurana* with *Rajavriksha Jala*
9. *Surasadi Gana Jala*^[41] – *Karna Prakshalana* and *Karnapurana* are performed with *Surasadi Gana Jala*
10. *Nari Kshira Mardita Rasanjana* with *Madhu* is indicated^[42].
11. *Kusthadya Taila*^[43]

F) Karnanadi

1. *Shambukadi Taila*^[44]
2. *Dhusturaadi Taila*^[45]

G) Krimikarna

1. *Krimiaphaha Yoga: Suryavart Swarasa, Sindhuvar Rasa, Langlimoola Rasa, Trayushana Churna*^[46] – *Karnapurana* is performed using these for management of *Krimikarna*
2. *Vartaka Dhooma*^[47] – *Karna Dhoopana*
3. *Sarshapa Taila Karnapurana*^[48]
4. *Yogadwayam*^[49]
 - i. *Langli, Suryavarta, Vyosha Swarasa* – *Karnapurana*
 - ii. *Neelabuhala, Taila, Sindhu Lavana, Kaanji* – *Karnapurana* is carried out after heating.

H) Karnapali Vardhana Yogas

1. *Vishgarbha Taila*^[50]
2. *Shatavaryadi Taila*^[51]
3. *Gunja Navanita Yoga*^[52] – massage on lobule.
4. *Jeevaniyaadi Tailam*^[53]
5. *Mushali Kanda Yoga*^[54]

I) *Durviddha Karna Yoga*

1. *Madhukadi Lepa*^[55]

DISCUSSION

The *Yogas* described in *Chakradatta* for *Karnaroga* reflect a practical, disease-specific and *Dosha*-oriented therapeutic approach, with emphasis on localized management. As ear disorders predominantly involve *Vata* and *Kapha* vitiation, most formulations are administered through *Karnapurana*, supported by procedures such as *Nasya*, *Karna Prakshalana*, *Dhoopana*, *Abhyanga* and *Lepa*.

In *Karnashoola*, pain arising from aggravated *Vata* with *Kapha* obstruction is managed using *Ushna* and *Tikshna* drugs such as *Shringavera*, *Ardraka*, *Lashuna*, *Arka* and *Hingu*, often combined with *Madhu*, *Saindhava Lavana* and *Taila* to enhance penetration and analgesic action. Medicated oils like *Hingwadi Taila* and *Kshara Taila* further facilitate *Dosha* pacification and pain relief.

Karnanada and *Karna Badhira* are primarily functional disorders associated with *Vata-Kapha* imbalance. The repeated use of *Katu Taila*, *Swarjikakshara Taila* and *Apamarga Kshara Taila* indicates the importance of *Lekhana* and *Srotoshodhana* actions to relieve obstruction and restore auditory function. The indication of *Nasya* highlights the anatomical and therapeutic relationship between the nose and ear.

In *Karnastrava* and *Pootikarna*, characterized by discharge and infection, the therapeutic focus shifts toward *Shodhana*, *Krimighna* and *Ropana* measures. Formulations containing *Kashaya* drugs, *Kshara*, medicated waters and *Dhoopana* help control discharge, eliminate infection and promote healing. The use of *Gomutra*, *Harital*, *Guggulu*, and *Panchavalkala* reflects the application of potent cleansing and antimicrobial principles.

Conditions such as *Karnanadi* and *Krimikarna* require penetrating and parasite-destroying therapies, achieved through *Tikshna Taila*, *Swarasa* and *Dhoopana*. In contrast, *Karnapali Vardhana* formulations emphasize *Brimhana* and tissue nourishment, while *Durviddha Karna* management focuses on local wound healing.

Overall, the *Karnaroga Yogas* of *Chakradatta* demonstrate a comprehensive and rational framework that integrates localized therapy with *Dosha* correction. Their systematic

application offers valuable guidance for effective management of ear disorders in contemporary Ayurvedic practice.

CONCLUSION

The *Yogas* described by *Chakradatta* demonstrate a comprehensive and well-structured therapeutic approach to the management of *Karnarogas*. The predominant use of *Karnapurana* underscores its significance in directly pacifying aggravated *Vata* and *Kapha* within the auditory canal and achieving localized therapeutic action. The inclusion of diverse dosage forms such as *Kshara*, *Taila*, *Swarasa* and substances of animal origin highlights the multimodal and versatile nature of Ayurvedic otological management. Adjunctive procedures including *Nasya*, *Dhoopana* and *Lepa* further strengthen the holistic treatment strategy by addressing associated pathology and enhancing therapeutic efficacy. Overall, *Chakradatta* presents a rich source of disease-specific *Yogas* for *Karnarogas*, with a clear emphasis on localized therapeutic interventions and judicious drug selection. These classical formulations continue to hold significant clinical relevance and provide a strong foundation for evidence-based Ayurvedic management of ear disorders.

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